

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

ENHANCING LOCAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ROADMAPS.

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May 20th, 2024.

Policy Statement

The InterAgency Institute advocates the creation and diffusion of digital transformation roadmaps by institutions involved in the promotion of the development of local communities, as we consider that those can benefit enormously from a strategic and effective implementation of new technologies. Such roadmaps should outline the strategic vision, resource requirements and allocation, stakeholder engagement efforts, risk management, and measures to ensure the long-term sustainability of the change's impact. In this way, policymakers can fully leverage digital technologies' benefits in transforming public service, promoting innovation, boosting the local economy, and improving local communities' general quality of life.

Background

The availability of information and its consummation into knowledge is the most critical enabler of resource management in societies (Zimmermann, 1933). Therefore, local development initiatives have much to gain from technologies that can increase information availability, power efficiency, and innovation across economic and social development.

As Gong and Ribiere (2021) assert, digital transformation is not just about adopting digital technologies, but about using them to bring about radical improvements and innovations in organizations. It involves strategically leveraging resources and capabilities to create value for stakeholders. This definition underscores the transformative power of digital technology, which can reshape how organizations function, their business models, and even societal norms.

Technology-based companies often employ roadmaps to guide the continuous development of their products, offering users a glimpse into the planned features. These roadmaps go beyond being mere project management tools; they serve as a commitment, aiding others in planning their enhancements in anticipation of the new digital services and standards environment that is about to unfold in their local communities.

Digital transformation roadmaps connect strategy, governance, and implementation steps to ensure efforts are coordinated and focused on what needs to be delivered.

By addressing things like funding, governance structures, regulations, and training needs, these roadmaps provide a structured way to navigate the complexities of a change that is heavily institutional and behavioral and has long-term consequences.

We share Rogers's (2016) argument that digital transformation is about technology and crafting innovative strategies that benefit everyone involved. Employing a vision that facilitates intensive collaborative work and the determination of the local communities, we can go through the transition period on the road to inclusive, resilient, and sustainable development through the shared vision, decision-making, and commitment to implementing the strategies.

In this policy brief, we aim to highlight the crucial role that digital transformation roadmaps play in driving local development. We will explore their many benefits, such as making service delivery more efficient, improving accessibility, promoting data-driven decision-making, and empowering citizens. We will also emphasize the importance of collaboration and partnerships among policymakers, stakeholders, and the broader community in championing and sustaining digital transformation efforts at the local level.

Findings

We draw from the documented literature and studies in our digital transformation (DGT) exploration (Bousdeskis & Kardaras, 2020; Huang et al., 2020; Pittaway & Montazemi, 2020). Digital transformation can be a journey of local development, where digital solutions merge with an existing analogical local setting to accelerate growth.

Even with this promise of transformation, we must recognize the challenges that come with it. Many organizations struggle with outdated systems, duplicated processes, and a lack of clear insights into their operations. This obstructs efficiency and poses risks, like failing to meet crucial business needs or regulatory requirements. Adapting to new practices or migrating data is not easy either—it often requires significant time and effort. With technology evolving rapidly, staying compliant with government regulations can feel like a constant uphill battle. These challenges are real and complex, underscoring the need for thoughtful strategies and practical solutions as we navigate the ever-changing digital transformation landscape.

Challenges also come from agency or conflict of interest. Digital processes may interfere with the interests of individuals in local institutions, which benefit from traditional methods to protect their position and power. This is mainly through digital processes that increase community participation and voting, democratizing local development decision-making. In that context, transparency is a remedy and can be supported through roadmaps.

There is plenty of evidence of the need for more clarity in public institutions' processes, and this problem can be addressed through digital transformation. In the UK, the National Audit Office found no visibility of the end-to-end processes in 80% of the governmental organizations they visited during their 2022/23 audits (NAO, 2023). However, the digital transformation process should be made visible; that is where a publicized roadmap plays a significant role.

Recommendations

Institutions responsible for local development should orchestrate digital transformation initiatives using complete roadmaps. Local development institutions can create those roadmaps by following the steps (based on Huang et al., 2020, adapted to the needs of regional development institutions) described below.

- **Defining the goals and objectives for digital transformation to meet local development needs and opportunities:** digital transformation roadmaps must account for using the right digital tools for the desired work. Institutions must define objectives that address actual economic and social issues and opportunities identified in their local communities. Generic roadmaps are prone to failure. Digital transformation should not be based on blind benchmarking and trend following but require a purposeful examination of actual needs to avoid frustration in the face of the effort-result cycles during its implementation.
- **Developing strategies to achieve those goals and objectives:** to achieve the defined goals and objectives, strategies, such as sequenced deliverables, should be designed in the most beneficial way possible. Technological, institutional, and behavioral changes should be in a logical process that facilitates the next deliverable, accounting for dependencies, increasing complexity, realistic lead times, and the influence of an ever-changing environment.

- **Determining potential projects for business services and process improvement, considering local inclinations:** each town, city, or locality has its aptitudes or inclinations to perform better in certain areas. Those should be respected and leveraged in determining the potential projects to be digitally transformed.
- **Underlining the role of innovation in local digital projects:** the digital transformation roadmap should not aim to provide all solutions to local problems. Instead, it should encourage innovation and review, fostering adaptability and flexibility in the solutions.
- **Prioritizing projects on impact versus likelihood of delivery basis:** projects should be prioritized according to their level of impact and the likelihood that their effect will be delivered. Resources are scarce, and needs are often urgent, so realistic decisions are critical to effectively transforming the local conditions.
- **Scheduling short-term and long-term digital service delivery:** setting firm dates for deliverables is critical for the roadmap's relevance. Sharing such commitments achieves coordination, creating immense value for companies, individuals, external parties, and others who must plan their projects to align with the new digital reality.

We think the steps above are a good starting point for creating a roadmap for digital transformation for local development. However, the particularities of the regional institutions may require different elements. The most important recommendation is to formulate realistic, adaptable roadmaps that foster the local entities' strong engagement and commitment to its delivery.

Conclusions

We advocate for the widespread adoption of digital transformation roadmaps by institutions vested in advancing local communities. These roadmaps serve as indispensable guides that publicize committed deliverables. Through their implementation, we can trigger a wave of transformative change, reforming public services, cultivating innovation, strengthening local economies, and enhancing our communities' overall quality of life.

This policy brief has underscored the essential role of information in driving societal progress. As we embrace digital transformation, we recognize its power to reshape organizational structures, business models, and societal norms. Moreover, we acknowledge the critical importance of roadmaps, not merely as project management artifacts but as symbols of commitment and enablers of collective progress.

Institutions responsible for local development must heed the call to action and orchestrate digital transformation initiatives with purpose and precision. Through a systematic approach encompassing goal definition, strategy development, project prioritization, and commitment to delivery, we can realize the full potential of digital transformation in local communities.

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